

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Initiatives at the University of Fort Hare: Cure or Plague?

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Introduction

There is a taken-for-granted assumption, especially in the industrial countries of the west—the “first world”—that information technology (IT) has the potential to change, in dramatic ways, the manner in which individuals manage their lives and businesses, and communicate to the outside world. Technology is a powerful force for change that has been likened to the electric light, the printing, manned flight or any other technologies that have fundamentally altered the world (Lewis, 1999, Oblinger and Verville, 1999, Williams et al, 2000). The result has been what is now known as the information explosion or knowledge revolution. Thus the generation, processing, dissemination and storage of data has taken a completely new complexion. There has been a radical (paradigm) shift in the manner in which offices, companies, institutions of learning (especially tertiary institutions); families and individuals manage their data. It is a shift that is characterized by a move away from relying on paper, files and filing cabinets for storing and disseminating information, to the use of electronic media—the Internet and electronic mail—e-mail, CD-ROMs, computer hard-drives and diskettes. Information required for business, education, research, communication, travel or leisure can now be easily accessed thanks to the proliferation of invaluable sites now available on the World Wide Web. The World Wide Web shatters barriers of time and space in the delivery of instruction (Gladieux and Swail, 1999). The reason, we are told, is that digital magnetic storage is less costly than paper and will continue to

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be the dominant medium of storage of active data (Oblinger and Verville, 1999).

This paper, which attempts to provide an alternative, rather skeptical view on the perceived benefits of IT assesses prospects for students at the University of Fort Hare to access and benefit from IT and other online facilities. The University of Fort Hare is a historically black university (HBU), sometimes referred to as a historically disadvantaged institution (HDI) located in the Province of the Eastern Cape. The Eastern Cape is known for a legacy of poor infrastructure, limited employment opportunities, large youthful populations and chronic poverty (*DistriIT Development Support Project*, 1999), and has been identified as the poorest of South Africa's nine provinces (*Measuring Poverty in South Africa*, 2000).

The paper comments on the poor geophysical context of Fort Hare and the nature of its student population. It interrogates the assumptions that IT brings individuals into the global community; empowers them through access to online facilities and information, and expedites research and academic as well as global networks. The paper argues for the qualification of these assumptions in so far as most connectivity to the Internet is confined to capital cities (Dzidonu, 1999, Jenson, 2000). The downside of this is that the majority of people living in poor rural areas of South Africa, such as the Eastern Cape are effectively excluded from the benefits of IT due to the absence of basic facilities such as telephone lines, and consequently inability to afford and/or access IT facilities. The paper briefly comments on the "global digital divide," understood to refer to inequalities between people, as signified by notions of information "haves" and "have-nots," and their ability, or inability to access and benefit from IT facilities. It argues that IT has the potential to accentuate existing inequalities in wealth between countries, as signified by the North/South divide, and the inability of most of the South to be active role players in the global agenda. It argues a case for inequalities in wealth between persons with reference to information "have-nots" and their inability to access and benefit from IT facilities and online resources.

The University of Fort Hare context

The view that while computers may seem ubiquitous in today's society their distribution is highly stratified by income, race and ethnicity, and educational attainment (Gladieux and Swail, 1999, 8) is very true to the University of Fort Hare in particular, and to the Province of the Eastern Cape in general. Fort Hare was founded in 1916 to provide access to higher education to predominantly black students from low socio-economic backgrounds drawn from the Eastern Cape, other neighboring provinces and from southern African countries. It is one of the nine HBU/HDIs created as part of the broad policy of the then apartheid regimes to segregate access to higher education. Like most of the HBU/HDIs that are located in former "independent" homelands, or "Bantustans,"¹ Fort Hare is located in Alice, a small, remote and poor town in the former homeland of Ciskei.

The “independent” homelands were segregated residential areas for different ethnic (tribal) groups. For instance Ciskei and Transkei, where the universities of Fort Hare and Transkei are located are both former “independent” homelands for Xhosa-speaking peoples. Lebowa and Bophuthatswana, where the universities of the North and Northwest are located are Pedi and Tswana-speaking areas respectively. Universities of Zululand and Durban Westville provide access to predominantly Zulu and Indian students in the province of Kwazulu-Natal. The University of Venda likewise provides higher education access to African students in what was then the homeland of Venda, while the University of the Western Cape services mostly colored students. These universities also fulfilled an economic cause as cheap labor pools for commercial farming, manufacturing and mining industries.

Overcrowding, high levels of illiteracy, insufficient resources and essential services such as clean running water, electricity, telecommunication, primary health care services and basic infrastructure characterize most of these former “independent” homelands. A situational analysis conducted by Research Triangle Institute noted that:

The Eastern Cape is one of the poorest provinces in South Africa, with about 70% of its 6.7 million-population living in the rural former homelands of Ciskei and Transkei. These two former homelands have a legacy of poor infrastructure, limited employment opportunities, large youthful populations and chronic poverty (*DistrIT Development Support Project*, 1999).

The province has just been singled out as the poorest in terms of average monthly household expenditure and most in need of infrastructural development such as clean water and sanitation and improvement of life circumstances such as employment creation and family planning (*Measuring Poverty in South Africa*, 2000).

Given these regional dynamics it is reasonable to infer that the majority of Fort Hare students are from predominantly rural and disadvantaged socio-economic backgrounds. They neither have the requisite skills nor the cultural propensity for computers and the Internet to be able to sufficiently benefit from limited IT and online facilities available at the university. The students’ precarious situation is exacerbated by the university’s disadvantaged context. Currently student enrollment at Fort Hare is just over 4000, having shrunk from almost 7000 in the past decade. The drop in student numbers in most public higher education institutions in South Africa is a result of a variety of factors, among which are:

- A) General uncertainty in the higher education sector as a result of the national ministry of education’s endeavor to transform the sector into a single coordinated system that is responsive to issues such as past inequities, lack of access to disadvantaged peoples and the need to redress such imbalances.
- B) Competition as a result of the proliferation of private higher education institutions that, together with Technikons, offer more job-oriented degree programs and guaranteed job placements.

- C) Huge problems of maladministration and financial mismanagement that plagued most HBU/HDI's in the past five years, and
- D) The recent tightening of control in so far as payment of fees and collection of student debts are concerned.

As a result of (c) above the University of Fort Hare is currently servicing a R50 million overdraft inherited from the previous management. In 1999 the figure was R90 million.

As recently as May 2001 the university's only public Internet access point, the Library, had only four PCs linked to the Internet and in good working condition. Based on current enrollment level of just over 4000 a simple mathematical analysis would suggest that there is only one Internet linked PC to every 1000 students. But considering that the Library has a two hours maximum PC booking arrangement for students, and that opening times are from 8 hours 30 to 22 hours, it follows that on any given day about 6 students would be able to access one PC. This translates to 24 students a day for the four PCs, which is a meager 0.6 percent access. But as has been argued, growth and development as a result of IT do not only come from buying computers, but from connecting them to each other (McConnell International, 2000, Tannenbaum, 1999). Indeed one of the key attributes of E-Readiness that was identified in a study by McConnell International (2000) is connectivity, taken to encompass:

- Availability of wireline and wireless communication services, community access centers (free and paid), and networked computers in business, schools, and homes.
- Affordability and reliability of network access including the cost of service, downtime, and the prevalence of sharing access among individuals.
- Underlying infrastructure, including the reliability of electrical supply for business-critical computer operations.

IT's Potential to Accentuate Inequalities

The globalization imperative requires potential role players not only to possess requisite IT skills, but also to have regular access to IT facilities. For the majority of students enrolled in traditionally white advantaged public higher education institutions, most of which are located in urban metropolitan areas,² IT skills and access to IT facilities are taken to be the norm. Their urban locality, for which IT skills and baseline facilities are *sine qua non*, necessarily predisposes them to becoming role players in the global digital community. The enduring relationships most of these universities have with business (the mining industry in the case of the University of the Witwatersrand in Johannesburg, and marine and shipping industries in the case of the Universities of Cape Town, Natal and Port Elizabeth) and large amounts of donor funding they are able to muster for research purposes, stand them in good stead to provide essential educational and support facilities for their students. The possibilities and opportunities created by these relationships can not only be seen in the attraction and market

credibility of their degrees, but also in the extent to which most of their students are almost ready to engage with the challenges of the rapidly globalizing world.

This however is a remote reality for the majority of black students enrolled at HBU/HDI's such as Fort Hare. Besides their disadvantage of being located in poor and rural areas, these universities have, in the past been pigeonholed and derogatively referred to as "bush" or "homelands" universities. As a consequence they have continued to be treated with disdain not only by national and international donor agencies, but also by the corporate world. This has had profound implications not only on the marketability of their institutional brand names, but also of their degrees and graduates in the job market. Inadequacy of requisite IT skills and IT facilities certainly predisposed their graduates to a severely disadvantaged start in the competition for jobs. Most job offers are conditional to potential employees' ability to use basic computer software such as Microsoft Word, Microsoft Excel, Microsoft PowerPoint, Microsoft Project 98 and WordPerfect, as well as being able to send, receive e-mail and surf the Internet for information.

Given the above-mentioned 0.6 percent probability for Fort Hare students to access computers and online facilities in the university's main IT public access point, which is the Library, it is reasonable to argue that the 99 plus percent that is unlikely to access these facilities for much of their duration of study would be excluded from global networks. Consequently their inability, as graduates, to operate a PC means they would be overlooked for those who have the requisite IT skills. This can only go on to accentuate existing inequalities in wealth and access to IT as well as the urban/rural divide. It seems to me that the dilemma faced by Fort Hare students and graduates should be seen as part of the larger IT picture known as the "global digital divide", to which I make brief remarks below. Two key aspects of the "global digital divide", namely (a) disparities in access to IT as a result of stratification in wealth levels, and (b) rapid advances in IT, shall be explored. Their overall consequence is that advanced countries will continue not only to be key players in technological advances and the global agenda, but will also continue to benefit from the above-mentioned rapid advances while poor countries and their disadvantaged institutions and students will continue to lag behind.

The global "digital divide"

Controversy over the global digital divide continues to grow as technological advances continue to gain momentum (*The Digital Planet 2000: The Global Information Economy*, 2000, Gladieux and Swail, 1999, Jenson, 2000, The National Telecommunications Information Association (NTIA), 1997, 1998, 1999, Lee, 2000, McConnell International, 2000, Singleton and Mast, 2000, Sullivan, 2000). In this section of the paper the notion of "global digital divide" shall refer to the ever-growing disparity in wealth and access to IT facilities and on-line information between rich and poor people—the

information “haves” and “have nots” and between rich countries of the North—the developed, first world countries, and the poor countries of the South—the underdeveloped, third world countries.

Disparities of Access

The Global Public Policy Conference, planned for September 2001 in Cape Town, South Africa, under the auspices of World Information Technology and Services Alliance (WITSA) and Information Industry South Africa (IISA) aims to generate debate and seek solutions to “bridge the gap” otherwise known as “The Digital Divide”. The Conference organizers recognize that:

As technology permeates every aspect of our lives in the modern world, it is increasingly affecting the lives of those in developing countries even though it may be less apparent. It is clear that in most instances advances in information technology and information are widening the gap between the first and third world countries and between the “haves” and the “have-nots” in populations <http://www.sbs.co.za/gppc/GPPC_INTRO.htm>.

The following are “Facts about the Digital Divide” the Conference seeks to investigate:

Access: There are more Internet hosts in New York City than on the continent of Africa.

Computing: Number of PCs per 1000 population:

Industrial countries:	156.3
Developing countries:	6.5

Networks: 80% of the world’s population lack access to reliable telecommunication systems.

Telephony: 75 % of the world’s telephones are in just 8 industrial countries.

Income: The share of global income of the richest 20 % is 74 times that of the poorest 20%.

Wealth: What top and bottom countries control:

	The top 20%	the bottom 20%
World’s GP	86%	1%
Global Export Market	82%	1%
Foreign Direct Investment	68%	1%
World’s Phone lines	74%	1.5%

Internet: Number of Internet hosts (in 1000’s):

Industrial countries:	15, 818
Developing countries:	435

<http://www.sbs.co.za/zppc/ZPPC_FACTS.htm>

It is clear from the above that while the developed countries can harness their wealth to turn provision of IT into the taken-for-granted norm, this may seem like an impossibility in most developing countries where 42 percent of the world's adult population has never used a telephone (Sullivan, 2000).

Yet mention should be made that even in industrial countries the situation of IT connectivity and access might not be as silver stair as the figures make it to appear. The 1998 survey by NTIA, "Falling Through the Net: New Data on the Digital Divide" noted that "the "digital divide"—the divide between those with access to new technologies and those without—is now one of America's leading economic and civil rights issues". It went on to posit that "a digital divide" still exists, and, in many cases, is actually widening over time. The survey noted that while penetration rates have risen across demographic groups and geographical areas, nevertheless they still differ substantially according to income, education level, race, household type, and geography. It noted that while "as a nation, Americans have embraced the Information Age through electronic access in their homes...the "digital divide" between certain groups of Americans has *increased* between 1994 and 1997 so that there is now an even greater disparity in penetration levels among some groups" ("Falling Through the Net", 1998, p.2).

In another study, Gladieux and Swail (1999) noted the rapid increase in electronic delivery of higher education in the United States as a result of a burgeoning computer market and the advent of the Internet and the World Wide Web. They quoted statistics from the US Education Department showing that in 1995 three-quarters of a million US students enrolled in more than fifteen thousand online distance education courses. However they caution that school access to the Internet is not a good indicator of students' access; that in half the schools that are linked to the Internet the connections are only at the library, media center, or in the Principal's office, and not the classrooms. Gladieux and Swail (1999) argued that the advent of the Internet might create new barriers and inequalities because of the differential availability of the required technology and the fact that access to online facilities is stratified by income. Case in point: households earning less than \$5,000 are the worst off: roughly one in four has no phone ("Falling Through the Net", 1998). Three-quarters of US households with incomes over \$75,000 have a computer, compared to one-third of households with incomes between \$25,000 and \$35,000, and one-sixth with incomes below \$15,000. Race has serious implications on the extent to which families are able to access IT facilities. "Overall, white households have a far higher telephone penetration rate (95.9%) than Black (86% or Hispanic (86.5) households. Whites are still more than twice as likely (40.8%) to own a computer than Blacks (19.3%) or Hispanics (\$19.%) ("Falling Through the Net", 1998).

What do these figures hold for the "global digital divide" debate in so far as Africa in general, and students at the University of Fort Hare in particular are concerned? Well, it might be argued, it seems like nothing but gloom.

And considering, as shown above, that New York City has more Internet hosts than the entire continent of Africa even though nearly 15 percent of the world's population is in Africa ("Facts about the digital divide", 2001, http://www.sbs.co.za/gppc/GPPC_FACTS.htm), the gloom thesis might have substance. The African continent possesses just 2 percent of the world's total number of telephones and less than 0.1 percent of Internet users ("Risk E-Business: Seizing the Opportunity of Global E-Readiness", 2000). In the sub-Saharan region alone there is one phone line for every 100 people while in the US the number is 4 lines per 100 people (Pape, 1999). These disparities are, as shown, linked to wealth. For instance while the US remains world leader in IT spending—\$762 billion in 1999 (*Digital Planet 2000*, 2000), the IT spending for the Middle East and Africa was \$18.2 billion. Of this South Africa spent \$10.6 billion ("Risk E-Business", 2000). As a consequence there are 156.3 PCs per 1000 in industrial countries while there is a meager 6.5 PCs per same number in developing countries ("Facts about the Global Digital Divide", 2001).

It should however be mentioned that the connectivity situation in Africa is improving. For instance as of November 2000 54 African countries and territories had achieved permanent connectivity and the presence of local full service dialup ISPs. Internet access however continues to be confined to capital cities (Dzidonu, 1999, Jenson, 2000). And as Dzidonu (1999:12) argues, this is mainly due to the poor telephone connections in remote regions. The Eastern Cape, in South Africa, whose large sections of the population—70 percent of its 6.7 million people, lives in rural, economically disadvantaged areas, is the case in point.

Rapid changes in IT

Rapid changes in IT are inescapable. Oblinger and Verville (1999) map out four major trends in IT which impact on business and higher education and which are crucial for life in the "networked world". These are digitization, storage, the increase in processing power, and universal communications.

(a) Digitization. Oblinger and Verville (1999) point out that information technology makes it possible to digitize information, whether text, images, sound or large data streams. This has allowed for virtually everything to be translated into a common currency of bits and bytes. They argue that powerful new communication technologies now make it possible to handle, at high speed, rich but space consuming digitized information such as video, medical images and works of art.

(b) Storage. Oblinger and Verville (1999) argue that the capacity of data storage is growing by 60 percent each year; data access rates are increasing dramatically; digital magnetic storage is less costly than paper and is poised to be the dominant medium for storage of active data. For instance texts of 375 average-size novels can now be stored in a single square inch of disk surface. Who would doubt the capacity of CD-ROMs to store text, images, full-motion video, electronic catalogues, games and software?

(c) **Processing Power.** The processing power at our disposal, Oblinger and Verville (1999) argue, has increased tremendously over time. This is expected to double every 18 months. A typical client microprocessor, they contend, will have the capability of today's large server.

(d) **Universal Communication.** Oblinger and Verville (1999) envisage a situation whereby IT will move beyond client-server computing and packet-based Internet connections to global connectivity. This, they contend, will profoundly change access to content, services and communication. They are excited about the advent of Personal area networks (PANs), Local area networks (LANs), Wide area networks (WANs), the use of radio frequency within individual buildings or small campuses, and infrared within rooms or other enclosed spaces, and how these would create a "networking revolution" for a "networked world".

These dramatic changes in IT are already impacting on business, industry and education. They are expediting the transmission of information, which Oblinger and Verville (1999) describe as "the currency of exchange in campus relationships". They are encouraging exchanges between research teams, between college applicants and admission departments. The bottom line, Oblinger and Verville (1999) argue, is that "change is immanent". In the next decade, they advise, IT and its effects as a transformation agent will have a dramatic impact on our lifestyles, workstyles and education. This makes the IT imperative ever crucial, even for disadvantaged communities such as those in the rural disadvantaged areas of the Eastern Cape in general, and the disadvantaged students of the University of Fort Hare in particular.

It should, however be pointed out that as with improvements in Africa's connectivity mentioned above, all is not that gloomy at Fort Hare after all. Concerted efforts to raise funds from external donors for the purpose of providing adequate IT facilities and of empowering both staff and students with requisite IT skills are beginning to pay dividends.

IT initiatives at Fort Hare

The uninspiring conditions at Fort Hare in particular, and in the Eastern Cape in general should not detract from a whole range of initiatives being undertaken by the university not only to provide access to computers and online facilities to staff and students, but also to address the issue of requisite IT skills. Here are some examples:

1. The Department of Computer Science has three laboratories—Multi-media, with 28 PCs, Honors, with 7 PCs, and Video Conferencing Room, with 9 PCs. While the Honors Lab is primarily for use by Computer Science Honors students there is provision for postgraduate students from other Faculties and Departments to access it for research purposes, by prior arrangement of course. This is an attempt to widen access to IT and expedite completion of research project by honors students across Faculties. This is important because the state's allocation of subsidy is doubled for every postgraduate student who completes his/her degree program.

2. In May 2001, Thintana Communication, a consortium of Telkom's foreign strategic equity partners formed in 1997, provided R5million funding to set up the Thintana Technology Center Project at Fort Hare. The Project aims to address the lack of IT skills among staff and students by providing training in information and computer literacy, multimedia course preparation and online delivery (*Daily Dispatch*, 26 May 2001, *The Transformation Focus* 2(5), 2001). The Technology Center shall provide for the establishment of the following:

- A student access Lab with 100 Internet linked PCs. It is expected that this would bring the ratio of student access to computers to 24:1.
- A teaching Laboratory with 50 PCs for Departments with IT requirements in their curricular, but to be open for use by other Faculties and Departments in the evening.
- A Unix Lab with 30 PCs for courses that run on the Unix operating system.
- A GIS remote sensing Lab with 30 PCs.
- An Information Literacy Lab with 50 PCs, to be housed in the university Library. This would be primarily for students of Library Information Literacy and for digital linking with other Libraries.
- A Postgraduate student Lab with 30 PCs, which would provide adequate resources for research. And finally
- A Multimedia open-access Lab in the Library with 20 PCs fitted with digital scanners, cameras, video-recorders, web-development software and multimedia tools

3. 100 PCs funded by the United States Agency for International development (USAID) for agricultural research would, as of July 2001, be distributed to needy academic staff as part of the university's broader IT initiative to widen access to computers and online facilities. The condition though is that each recipient would develop a course that would be available online.

4. All these fancy initiatives amount to naught if network accessibility is unreliable. To that end the university has set aside R1.2million a year for the purpose of increasing its bandwidth from 64kbps to 2Mbps (2000kbps). This would provide a speedy and consistent Internet connection that would not only enable the university to have teleconferencing facilities, but will also facilitate networks between Fort Hare staff and students and fellow staff and students from other universities nationally and internationally.

Are these initiatives sufficient to prepare Fort Hare graduates for challenges of the rapidly globalizing environment? It might be argued that it is not cost effective to simply provide state-of-the-art IT facilities without ensuring that potential users are equipped with requisite skill to enable them to access and benefit from such facilities. Indeed it is common practice in most of the developing world for huge amounts of money to be spent on sophisticated technology without sufficiently providing the recipients with the requisite skills not only to use the gadgets but also to maintain them. Cognizant of these criticisms, Fort Hare's Computer Literacy Project is offering, on regular basis throughout the year a four weeks "Introduction to Computing" course in collaboration with the Computer

Science and the Computer Science Society, for R350. This is a very basic course with hands-on-tutorials covering a wide range of simple stuff such as logging on to a computer, using the mouse and perfecting the technique of “double-clicking” on icons, accessing word-processing programs such as Microsoft Word, Microsoft PowerPoint, Microsoft Excel, WordPerfect, Corel, etc., opening a page, creating a document, saving it and retrieving it. The course is structured as follows:

- Introduction to Computers
- Windows NT 4.0 Workstation
- Disk Operating System (DOS)
- Word-Processing: Word 2000
- Spread-Sheet: Excel 2000
- Electronic Mail: Microsoft Outlook, and Internet – Internet Explorer 5.0 (Keyise, 2000, “Introduction to Computing: with hand-on tutorials”).

The idea is to get staff and students to possess the basics of computing. Taking this to another level, of expanding one’s interactions with IC and being part of wider global networks will depend on one’s initiative and enthusiasm.

Conclusion

This paper set out to provide a skeptical perspective to the view that IT has the potential to bring people into the global community. While not doubting the merits of IT’s capabilities it proposed that such claims be qualified in view of disparities in the distribution of wealth between nations and between peoples. It focused attention on the plight of students at the University of Fort Hare, in the Eastern Cape, which is the poorest of South Africa’s nine provinces. It argued instead that IT has the likelihood of accentuating instead of bridging existing inequalities in wealth between countries and between peoples. It contended that not ‘everybody’ is predisposed to becoming a role player in the global agenda given that access to IT and online facilities is stratified by income. This, the paper posited, is most likely to exacerbate the “global digital divide”—the growing disparity in wealth between countries of the North and the South, and between peoples, the information “haves” and “have-nots”. The U.S.’s 1999 expenditure on IT, which stood at \$762 as opposed to South Africa’s expenditure in the same year, which was \$10.6, illustrates the “divide”. But while on the surface the University of Fort Hare’s situation seemed very gloomy, the paper outlined positive, but modest initiatives not only to provide access to IT and online facilities, but also to quip staff and students with requisite skills to enable them to be role players in the global agenda.

Notes

1. Exceptions are the Universities of Durban-Westville and Western Cape, which are in urban areas. It should however be mentioned that their urban location did not exempt them from the state’s segregation policies prior to 1994.

2. Examples are the Universities of the Witwatersrand (Wits), in Johannesburg, Natal, in Durban, Pretoria, and Cape Town.

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